

Interoperability for the Implementation of Workflows for Structural Modeling, Analysis, and Design

AZINWIE ZAMA AMBE

Supervisors:

Tomo Cerovšek

Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Primož Može

Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Abstract

Building Information Modelling (BIM) has unique advantages and potential in structural engineering. Its methodology supports collaborative work based on the centralisation of all information in the federated BIM model and an efficient level of interoperability between BIM-based platforms. However, for structural modelling, analysis and design workflow, the interoperability capacity of the most used software presents limitations that must be resolved with immediate solutions. These significant challenges hinder implementing BIM workflows in a structural BIM design office. This study seeks to analyse the process of transferring structural models and data between modelling, structural analysis, and design tools while developing a unique workflow for implementation within these tools, BIM platforms, and design teams. A case study has been developed to test a practical interoperability workflow between Trimble Tekla Suite (Tekla Structural Designer, Tekla Structure, and Tekla Tedds), SCiA Engineer, Revit, and IDEA StatiCa. This is to identify and fix the limitations involved in the transfer processes of data flow between these specific structural BIM software. The information and model transfer processes are bilateral, using the native data format and the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), the universal standard data transfer format. Structural

BIM modelling and design maturity are relatively underutilised. This is mainly due to interoperability problems. Despite the identified limitations and challenges, the study outcomes within the case study development illustrate how the workflow has excellent advantages in developing structural BIM projects and its implementation in a structural BIM design office.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/HMDZbM2h9P8>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7261730